

POLKESMED PRIMARY CLINIC ADVANTAGE AS PRACTICE CLINIC VEHICLE TO IMPROVE STUDENT MIDWIFERY COMPETENCY

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Abstract

Clinical competencies as follows experience have a positive effect on the preparation of new midwifery in clinical practice, as a place for them to gain expertise. This study aims to find out the ability of midwifery students who were tested for their skills at the Polkesmed clinic and Puskesmas Pancur Batu. This was a comparative study, pre and post-test design, using primary data. Data were taken from the ANC test of student midwifery, collected sampling of two groups by *purposive sampling*, consisting of 120 respondents (each group was 60). Analysis data used pair T-test and Mann-Whitney Test. The results before clinic Polkesmed was revised ANC test was 73.23. After the intervention, the average value of student competency ANC was 79.55. The results of the analysis in Puskesmas Pancur Batu before intervention was 72.61 after the intervention was 89.12. Competency scores of students who practice at the Polkesmed Clinic and Puskesmas Pancur Batu, where the average value of the competence ANC students for the Polkesmed clinic is 80. Furthermore, research can be continued research competency of other student majors at the Polkesmed Clinic, and student competency in several other clinics.

Keywords: Student Competency Midwifery, Vehicle Practice Clinic, Primary Clinic.

INTRODUCTION

Based on stated that Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed by themselves, society, nation, and state ⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾⁽³⁾.

Learning is a process of interaction between students and educators and learning resources in a learning environment. Types of education include general, vocational, academic, professional, religious, and special education. Based on the Regulation of the Minister of Health number 71 of 2013 concerning Health Services in the National Health Insurance, it is stated that the first-level health facilities in collaboration with BPJS Kesehatan are required to provide comprehensive health services. These comprehensive health services are promotive, preventive, curative, rehabilitative health services, midwifery services, medical emergency health services, and support services which include simple laboratory examinations and pharmaceutical services in accordance with the provisions of the legislation. For health facilities that do not have supporting facilities, they are required to build a network with supporting facilities, if necessary, referrals to other supporting facilities are necessary ⁽⁴⁾⁽⁵⁾.

Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health Medan is one of the Vocational Health Education Institutions, which applies a larger proportion of practical curriculum than theory. The application of practice is carried out through experimental learning to educational mediums that will help students to integrate theory and practice ⁽⁵⁾⁽⁶⁾⁽⁷⁾⁽⁸⁾.

The limited facilities for health education in North Sumatra which are not matched by an increase in the number of students in the health sector each year, as well as the urgency of developing and optimizing Clinics, are the basis for Polkesmed to make this an opportunity to be able to improve and develop health services both in terms of facilities and infrastructure and optimizing the use of Polkesmed clinics as one of the Health Education Mediums ⁽⁹⁾. The development of Clinic or Polkesmed clinics as a medium for practice has two functions, namely as a laboratory and clinical-based learning facility.

This practice medium provides a comprehensive learning program in accordance with the national curriculum and local content that is integrated with the world of work ⁽⁷⁾. Learning includes hard skills work skills, language skills, complementary and entrepreneurship, while still emphasizing mastery of soft skills work ethics, communication, using learning methods or media, campus management practices, developing research results, and community service practices. Besides that, in carrying out the education process for health workers, laboratory skills are needed. The availability of appropriate laboratory skills greatly assists students in applying the theory and practice they have acquired from the lecture hall and from the laboratory room in a real setting so as to achieve competence in accordance with the demands of the curriculum ⁽¹⁰⁾⁽¹¹⁾⁽¹²⁾⁽¹³⁾⁽¹⁴⁾.

The Polkesmed Clinic is an implementing element of some of the duties of Polkesmed in the field of health services which are under and directly responsible to the Director. The establishment of this medical center is because health is the most dominant factor in the lives of our people, For that we need an institution or center that can handle services in the health sector by looking at the potential that exists in the ME facilities and Tuntungan District area, both the potential for Human Resources (HR), environmental potential and population potential in 2015 reached 85,615 people ⁽¹⁵⁾⁽¹⁶⁾.

The Weisbord theory approach was also carried out by Polkesmed in analyzing problems and the potential development of the units needed to improve health and education services. The results of the analysis show that the Polkesmed Clinic Unit is a unit that has the highest level of urgency to be improved and optimized in an effort to improve the performance of Polkesmed health services. This is in line with the health transformation program of the Indonesian Ministry of Health, namely increasing the capacity and capability of primary services ⁽¹⁷⁾⁽¹⁸⁾⁽¹⁹⁾⁽²⁰⁾⁽²¹⁾. Based on Regulation of Government RI number 13 of 2015 about the National Standard of Education stated that Competence is a set of attitudes, knowledge, and skills, which must be owned, internalized, and controlled by students after studying a content learning, completing a program, or completing an educational unit certain. Graduate Competency Standards are criteria regarding the qualifications of graduates' abilities which include attitudes, knowledge, and skills ⁽²²⁾⁽²³⁾.

Clinical competencies as follow experience that has a positive effect on the preparation of new nurses in clinical practice, as a place for new nurses to gain expertise and to be more successful in achievement, and help to realize educators and leaders have an understanding of the relationship between performances based on clinical competence. Puskesmas Pancur Batu owned by the government provides primary services to the community, besides that it is a vehicle for Polkesmeds' midwifery student practice, specifically for Ante Natal Care (ANC) examinations. Based on the explanation above, researchers are interested in finding out the difference in the ability of midwifery students who were tested for their skills at the Polkesmed clinic and Puskesmas Pancur Batu.

METHODS

This type of research is a comparative study, designed for pre-, and post-test, data collection using primary data. Data were taken from the result competency test of practice Ante Natal Care (ANC) student midwifery. This research was conducted for 2 years from 2016 - 2017 at the Health Polytechnic Clinic of the Ministry of Health Medan. The population in this study were all students in the third level (the sixth semester) at the Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health Medan. The sampling method in this study was *purposive sampling*, there were 120 respondents that met the inclusion criteria.

The inclusion criteria are as follows active Students of the Midwifery D-III Study Program in Medan, students who have passed Semester I-V courses, students who are in Semester VI, and students who have passed the Midwifery Laboratory Test course. To compare the results of the competence of students who practice at the Clinic Poltekkes Medan Batu Health Center Pancur performed the Mann-Whitney Test This research was carried out after obtaining a research ethics feasibility letter from the Ethics Committee of the University of North Sumatra. This research was also carried out after obtaining approval from respondents as evidenced by affixing the respondent's signature to the research approval sheet ⁽²⁴⁾ ⁽²⁵⁾.

RESULTS

The analysis results obtained an average value of student competence in practicing midwifery care for pregnant women at the Clinic Polkesmed before the intervention was 73.23 (72.57-73.89), with a standard deviation of 2.56. Range value between 70 and highest 80. From the interval estimation results it can be concluded that 95% are believed to be the average value of student competence in Medan Health Polytechnic Of Ministry of Health clinics between 72.57 and 73.89.

After the intervention, the average value of student competency in practicing midwifery care for pregnant women in Medan Health Polytechnic Of Ministry of Health clinics was 79.55 (78.59-80.51), with a standard deviation of 3.73. The lowest value is 70 and the highest is 88. From the interval estimation results it can be concluded that 95% are believed to an average student competency value after an intervention between 78.59 and 80.51 (see Table 1).

Table 1: Average distribution of student competency scores ANC (Antenatal Care) Practice of Midwifery Department at Clinic Polkesmed in 2017

Variable	Mean	Deviation Standart	Min-Max	95 % CI	N
Value before treatment	73.23	2.56	70-80	72.57-73.89	60
Value after treatment	79.55	3.73	70-88	78.59-80.51	60

Table 2: Average distribution of student competency scores ANC (Antenatal Care) Practice of Midwifery Department at Pancur Batu Health Center in 2017

Variable	Mean	Deviation Standart	Min-Max	95 % CI	N
Value before treatment	72.61	1.80	70-75	72.14-73.09	57
Value after treatment	89.12	5.32	80-96	89.71-90.54	57

The results of the analysis obtained an average value of student competence in practicing midwifery care for pregnant women in Pancur Batu Public Health Centre before intervention was 72.61 (72.14-73.09), with a standard deviation of 1.80. The lowest score is 70 and the highest is 75. From the interval estimation results it can be concluded that 95% are believed to be the average competency value of students in Pancur Batu Public Health Centre between 72.14-73.09. After the intervention, the average value of student competency in practicing midwifery care for pregnant women in Pancur Batu Public Health Centre was 89.12 (89.71-90.54), with a standard deviation of 5.32. the lowest value is 80 and the highest is 96. From the interval estimation results it can be concluded that 95% are believed to be the average value of student competence after an intervention is between 89.71-90.54.

Student's competency data were analyzed to compare their skills to practice ANC at clinic Polkesmed and Puskesmas Pancur Batu according to the result their final examination as table below.

Table 3: Result Student Competency of Practicing ANC (Antenatal Care) Midwifery Department Health Polytechnic Medan 2017

No	Clinic	N	Means of grade ANC	Predicate Value	Mann-Whitney (P Value)
1	Clinic Polkesmed	60	80	A	0,000
2	Pancurbatu Health Centre	57	89	A	

The selection of the Mann Whitney test was based on the results of the homogeneity test, the data were not normally distributed. Based on the results of the Mann Whitney test, it showed that there was a significant difference between the competency scores of students who practice at the Polkesmed Clinic and the Competence scores of Students at the Pancur Batu Health Center, where the average value of the competence of antenatal care (ANC) students for the Polkesmed clinic is 80 (based on the mean rank 34.93) while the average value at the Pancur Batu Health Center was 89 (based on the mean rank of 84.34). However, the value of ANC at the Polkesmed Clinic is lower than Puskesmas (Centre of Health Community) of Pancur Batu, but based on the predicate value according to the provisions of the Academic Guidelines at the Poltekkes Kemenkes Medan, both the competency scores at the Polkesmed Clinic or at the Pancur Batu Health Center got the same result, namely A (range of grades (68-78) Good and

(79-100) Very Good (Academic Guide Poltekkes RI Ministry of Health Republic of Indonesia FY 2018 / 2019,2018) .

DISCUSSION

Competence of midwifery students and nutrition majors can be achieved by practicing at the Medan Health Polytechnic of Ministry of Health Clinics so that the clinic can be used as a medium for the practice of Medan Health Polytechnic of Ministry of Health Clinics students. Based on the results of the Mann Whitney test, it showed that there was a significant difference between the competency scores of students who practice at the Polkesmed Clinic and the Competence scores of Students at the Pancur Batu Health Center, where the average value of the competence of antenatal care (ANC) students for the Polkesmed clinic is 80 (based on the mean rank 34.93) while the average value at the Pancur Batu Health Center was 89 (based on the mean rank of 84.34). This is a natural thing because the Polkesmed clinic is still in the development process and is almost the same as the Pancur Batu Health Center. Therefore, although the Polkesmed clinic is still new, from the results of the student competency test, the clinic can already be used as a practice area for midwife students specifically for ANC practice. In line with the health transformation of the role of the Polkesmed in the fifth pillar, one of which is preparing professional staff who are reliable in providing health services, especially in this study a sample test was carried out for the midwifery profession. Polkesmed has several departments, one of which is the midwifery department which will produce professional midwives. The role of the Polkesmed Clinic in producing professional midwives is as a vehicle for special midwifery practice for antenatal care (ANC) services for pregnant women. The results of this research indicate that the Polkesmed Clinic can be developed as a vehicle for practice not only for midwifery majors but also for other departments within the Polkesmed environment. This statement is based on the predicate value of the ANC practice of students majority in midwifery at the Polkesmed Clinic is A (Very good), although the point value (number) of students' ANC practice at the Polkesmed Clinic (average score 80) with the Pancurbatu Health Center (average score 89) shows a significant difference. However, this is not a fundamental difference because the range of values for the two is in the very good predicate or A⁽²⁶⁾⁽²⁷⁾.

This is consistent with previous research that states more than 73% of students passed the examination of clinical skills securing more than 50% marks in each module. Clinical education is an essential part of medical trainees' education process, and curriculum planners agree that it should be based on ethical standards and principles in the medical field⁽²⁸⁾. Previous studies showed students expressed a higher level of satisfaction with their training experiences⁽²⁹⁾. Findings showed a significant difference in mean patient scores and professional role scores. Nurses who met the criteria for problem management had significantly higher scores on the patient care scale and the professional role scale than those who did not meet the criteria. Nurses with previous work experience (44%) were more likely to meet the criteria for problem management⁽³⁰⁾. A major determinant of the effectiveness of clinical teaching is the context in which it occurs⁽³¹⁾. Clinical teaching is performed by a faculty within a curriculum that is planned dan offered in response to professional, societal, and educational

expectations and demands, using available human, intellectual, physical, and financial resources context of the curriculum. Therefore, the practice of clinical teaching differs somewhat from program to program⁽³²⁾. It is not possible to recommend a set of clinical teaching strategies that will be equally effective in every education program. Rather, the faculty must make decisions about clinical teaching that are congruent with the planned curriculum and relevant to its context⁽³³⁾. Employers and societies increasingly ask for competent and ready-to-work graduates, endowed with a certain amount of capabilities and competencies when entering the workforce. Whereas the need for the highly skilled worker has been climbing, the discrepancy between the competencies of graduates and qualifications searched by employers continue to be a serious concern among various nations^{(34) (35) (36)}.

CONCLUSION

There was a significant difference in ANC practice scores ($p < 0.005$) in students who took exams at the Pancur Batu Health Center and the Polkesmed clinic, even though the predicate value was still in category A. There is no significant relationship between optimizing educational facilities and increasing the competence of students who practice at the Polkesmed Clinic compared to students who practice at the Pancur Batu Health Center. Further research can be done by comparing health services at the Medan Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health Clinic with several other clinics in Medan. Another hand can be continued research competency other student majors at the Medan Health Polytechnic of Ministry of Health Clinic, student competency in several other clinics.

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